

FLOATFARM
NEXT GENERATION FLOATING WIND FARMS

DELIVERABLE D3.2

Repositioning control solution capable of relocating a floating turbine within a wind farm

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January 2026

Document Track Information

Project information	
Project title	Developing the Next Generation of Environmentally-Friendly Floating Wind Farms with Innovative Technologies and Sustainable Solutions
Starting date	01.01.2024
Duration	48 months
Programme	HORIZON EUROPE
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01
Grant Agreement No	101136091

Deliverable information	
Deliverable number	3.2
Work package number	3
Deliverable title	Repositioning control solution capable of relocating a floating turbine within a wind farm
Lead beneficiary	Delft University of Technology
Author	L. Starink, J. Saverin, J.W. van Wingerden
Due date	31-01-2026
Actual submission date	31-01-2026
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Revision information			
Version	Contributors	Date	Description
v1	LS, JWvW.	16.01.26	First draft
v1.1	Sowento	29.01.26	Review 1
v2	LS, JWvW	30.01.26	Second draft

Funded by
the European Union

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About FLOATFARM

The **FLOATFARM** project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe program. This project is closely linked to the **FLOATECH** project (2020-2023) and aims to bring the technologies developed within FLOATECH to the next level of technological readiness, complementing them with a significant number of new concepts, innovations and methods. **FLOATFARM** aims to significantly advance the maturity and competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) technology by increasing energy production, achieving significant cost reductions within the design and implementation phases, improving offshore wind value chain and supporting EU companies in this growing sector. Additionally, **FLOATFARM** aims to decrease negative environmental impacts on marine life and to enhance the public acceptability of FOW, thereby accelerating the EU energy transition. The **FLOATFARM** consortium is coordinated by the Technische Universität Berlin and is made up of 17 partners spread across 8 countries, each contributing to technology and scientific excellence in the wind energy sector.

The approach of **FLOATFARM** can be broken down into three actions:

1. **Turbine Technology:** Development of innovative technologies and methods for improvements on an individual FOW turbine level,
2. **Farm Technology:** Development, investigation and demonstration of technologies that are applicable to an array of turbines within a FOW farm,
3. **Environmental & Socioeconomic Impacts:** Model development, data collection and scenario analysis of environmental, economic and sociological impacts of FOW farms.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Offshore wind energy is an increasingly growing source of renewable energy [11]. Since 2010, the total installed capacity has increased from 3.1GW to over 82.9GW, and the levelized cost of energy has reduced by 62% [16]. To continue this growth in the coming decades, it is important to realize that many of the locations that are favorable to offshore wind energy are situated in areas where the water depth is too large for the installation of bottom-fixed wind farms. Floating wind energy is therefore a crucial technology to expand offshore wind energy to deeper waters.

The power output of wind farms is negatively affected by wake interactions within the farm; as upstream turbines extract energy from the wind, downstream turbines experience a lower wind speed and consequently produce less power. Offshore wind farms are especially susceptible to this, as in offshore areas the wind has a lower turbulence intensity, causing turbine wakes to recover slower compared to onshore wind farms. To mitigate this effect, several wind farm flow control (WFFC) techniques have been developed. Examples are wake mixing techniques like the pulse [12] and the helix [10], which are designed to destabilize the wake, and yaw steering [8], which deflects the wake away from downstream turbines.

Floating wind farms have the possibility of a unique mechanism to mitigate the wake effect: turbine repositioning. In contrast to fixed-bottom turbines, floating wind turbines are not rigidly connected to the seabed, but are held in place by mooring lines which allow the turbine a range of movement. Turbine repositioning uses this range of movement to reposition turbines to minimize wake effects in the farm. The control problem for turbine repositioning is different to that of other WFFC techniques, because for turbine repositioning also the downstream turbine benefits from control, as it can be repositioned out of the wake of an upstream turbine. Therefore, in essence, turbines need to *cooperate* to maximize the power production of the farm. How this is achieved best is the topic of this deliverable.

The methodology of this task is summarized as follows. As anticipated in the task description, this task is subdivided into two steps. First, an exploratory step that investigates *what* models, and *which* control solutions are suitable for the adequate design of turbine repositioning techniques, which is the subject of Chapter 2. As a second step, these control methods are used to achieve cooperative control for a two-turbine wind farm, which is the subject of Chapter 3 and Chapter 4. As part of this second step, the QBlade simulation environment [7], in combination with the SailFFish wake model [27], which form a higher fidelity simulation environment than used in Chapter 2, is used to evaluate and validate the models used in the first step. Each of the chapters is now briefly introduced.

In Chapter 2 repositioning control is explored using simple nonlinear models, and linear analysis. It is shown that the mooring configuration of a floating wind farm is a determining factor for turbine repositioning. Current research on turbine repositioning is concentrated around floating wind farms where mooring lines are significantly lengthened to enhance the repositioning. However, excessive lengthening of the mooring lines is undesirable, as the design of conventional mooring systems already faces challenges regarding fatigue loads and costs [21]. Therefore Chapter 2 researches the effect of mooring line tension on the effectiveness of turbine repositioning. The yaw angles for a two-turbine wind farm are optimized for various mooring configuration, and it is found that the optimal repositioning strategy critically depends on the mooring configuration. In this chapter a novel technique, named dynamic repositioning, is presented, which increases the effectiveness of turbine repositioning for medium-taut mooring configurations.

In Chapter 3, the findings of the preceding chapter are tested in the QBlade-SailFFish coupling developed in Task 3.1 of this project [28]. The dynamic repositioning technique is implemented, and it is tested how the downstream turbine is best controlled when the incoming wake is dynamically changing over time. For this purpose, a data-driven extremum seeking control implementation is proposed, which calibrates the phase of the actuation of the downstream turbine for dynamic repositioning.

Chapter 4 investigates the synchronization of the helix for a three turbine wind farm. Similar to Chapter 3, the wake is dynamically changing over time, and the phase of the actuation of the second turbine is optimized to maximize the total power produced by the farm. Based on the phase of the Helix on the second turbine, the Helix on the second turbine interacts constructively or destructively with the incoming wake, which affects the power of the third turbine downstream.

The research performed for Chapters 2 and 3 is presented in two scientific publications. Chapter 2 is published in the peer-reviewed and accepted 2025 EERA Deepwind paper [30], and Chapter 3 forms a publication in preparation for the 2026 conference for control technology and applications (CCTA), which will be submitted on February 8th. Both papers are included verbatim in this document.

2 DEVELOPMENT OF TURBINE REPOSITIONING CONTROL STRATEGIES BASED ON MOORING LINE STIFFNESS

2.1 Introduction

Offshore wind energy has become a cornerstone in the transition to renewable energy sources. With a current installed capacity of 35 GW in Europe, and a planned installed capacities of 60 GW and 300 GW in 2030 and 2050, wind energy is scheduled to grow exponentially in the coming decades [32]. Installation sites that are favorable for wind energy, meaning that they have high average wind speed and shallow water depth, to facilitate this growth are however not abundantly available. The benefit of floating wind farms (FWFs) is that they expand the attainable wind energy resources immensely by enabling farms to be installed in deeper waters, where conventional bottom fixed installation is economically unattractive.

Within a wind farm, wind turbines experience reduced wind speeds when the wind direction aligns with the location of upstream turbines in the farm. Because, as an upstream turbine extracts energy from the wind, it leaves behind an area of low wind speed, which a downstream turbine experiences. This is known as the wake effect. Wind farm control methods that mitigate the wake effect, e.g. wake steering, have mainly been studied for bottom-fixed wind turbines. Floating wind turbines (FWTs) offer additional degrees of freedom, as each turbine can move within the constraints of its mooring lines. This mobility can be leveraged for wake steering, allowing turbines to be repositioned in the crosswind direction to prevent the wake from overlapping with downwind counterparts. By adjusting the turbine's yaw angle, a misalignment with the incoming wind is created, resulting in an aerodynamic force component in the crosswind direction, which facilitates the repositioning [14, 13].

Preliminary results on turbine repositioning indicate promising increases in wind farm efficiency [18, 19]. However, they also highlight the need to significantly reduce mooring line tension to enable a range of movement sufficient for the effective implementation of this technique. Furthermore, it has become clear that wake steering for FWFs is different to the fixed-bottom case in two key ways. First, the downstream turbines can also benefit from yaw misalignment, as it can move itself out of the wake of an upstream turbine. Second, yaw misalignment steers the wake in one direction, but repositions the turbine in the opposite direction. Because these mechanisms counteract each other, this can negate the wake steering effect [25]. The effect of floating turbine repositioning is currently mainly assessed using steady-state wake models. In this way wake dynamics are not modeled, and it is only possible to optimize the yaw angles such that they yield the optimal turbine repositioning in steady-state. Preliminary work on turbine repositioning with

a dynamic wake model is done, but only considers the case where mooring lines are significantly lengthened [20]. To better understand wake steering for floating wind turbines, the motivation for this work is to analyze turbine repositioning with dynamic models, while also considering the stiffness of the mooring configuration.

Therefore, this work contributes in two key ways; namely 1) by evaluating the effect of including wake dynamics in the assessment of turbine repositioning, and 2) by assessing the effect of the stiffness of the mooring configuration on turbine repositioning when wake dynamics are included. In this paper it is investigated how the mooring configuration influences the floater dynamics, and how these dynamics influence the optimal turbine repositioning solution. The presented work uses the dynamic wake model FLORIDyn [3] to include wake dynamics and thereby find optimal time-varying yaw signals. An FWT model with a semi-submersible platform is coupled with FLORIDyn to identify optimal yaw actions over time for a two-turbine FWF across a finite time horizon.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: first the simulation environment is introduced in Section 2.2 by introducing the floating turbine model and FLORIDyn. The optimization problem is defined in Section 2.3, and finally, the results are analyzed and presented in Section 2.4.

2.2 Description of the simulation framework

To define a simulation environment, this section first covers a simplified floater model based on the work of Homer and Nagamune [15]. This floater model captures the surge and sway dynamics of the turbines, and is coupled to FLORIDyn, which models wakes and the dynamic interaction between wakes. Next, FLORIDyn and the coupling between the floater model and FLORIDyn are covered. This section is concluded by covering the details regarding the wind farm layout and simulation settings used for the results in the remainder of this work.

2.2.1 Modeling of the floater dynamics

A simple floater model is derived by considering all forces that act on the platform, and by using these forces to construct the differential equation that governs the dynamics

$$m\ddot{p} = F_{\text{aero}}(\dot{p}, v(p), \gamma) + F_{\text{hydro}}(\dot{p}) + F_{\text{mooring}}(p), \quad (2.1)$$

where p is the position vector of the turbine consisting of the displacement in sway and surge direction. The time derivative of p is denoted by \dot{p} , and all forces on the right hand side of the equation are nonlinear functions that depend on p , \dot{p} , the turbine's yaw angle γ , and the effective wind speed at the turbine location $v(p)$. The mass m represents the combined mass of the turbine, the floater, and added mass

resulting from Morison's equation on which will be commented in Section 2.2.1.2. Each of the forces will now be defined in more detail.

2.2.1.1

The aerodynamic thrust force models the thrust force that acts on the rotor, and is a function of the turbine's yaw angle, the effective wind speed at the location of the turbine, and the turbine's velocity. The modeling of the aerodynamic thrust force follows the vortex cylinder model of a yawed actuator disc [5], and is defined as:

$$F_{\text{aero}}(\dot{p}, v(p), \gamma) = \frac{1}{8} \pi \rho_a D^2 C_T(\dot{p}, v(p), \gamma) \|\dot{p} - v\|_2^2 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\gamma) \\ \sin(\gamma) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.2)$$

where D is the rotor diameter, ρ_a is the air density, and C_T is the thrust coefficient that is modeled as

$$C_T(\dot{p}, v(p), \gamma) = 4a \left(\cos \gamma_{\text{rel}} + \tan \frac{p}{2} \sin \gamma_{\text{rel}} - a \sec^2 \frac{X}{2} \right). \quad (2.3)$$

Here, a is the axial induction factor which is fixed to $1/3$, $\gamma_{\text{rel}} = \gamma - \arctan \frac{v_x - \dot{p}_x}{v_y - \dot{p}_y}$ is the relative yaw angle, and $X = (0.6a + 1)\gamma_{\text{rel}}$ is the wake skew angle immediately past the rotor. The thrust coefficient is modeled while taking into account the relative wind speed, and the relative yaw angle experienced by the turbine caused by the velocity of the turbine itself.

2.2.1.2

The hydrodynamic forces that act on the platform are modeled using Morison's equation. The simulations in this work are performed under the condition of no current in the water. Hence, all hydrodynamic drag results from the velocity of the turbine itself. The hydrodynamic drag force is modeled as

$$F_{\text{hydro}}(\dot{p}, \ddot{p}) = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A_d \dot{p}}_{\text{Drag force}} - \underbrace{\rho_w C_m A_m \ddot{p}}_{\text{Mass force}}, \quad (2.4)$$

with ρ_w the density of water, and the coefficients C_d , A_d denoting the drag coefficient and reference area for the drag term, and C_m , A_m denoting the drag coefficient and reference area for the mass term. The hydrodynamic force can be split into a drag term that is related to the velocity of the floater, and a hydrodynamic mass term proportional to the floater acceleration. As mentioned earlier, the mass term is incorporated into the total mass at the left hand side of Equation 2.1, since it is proportional to the acceleration of the turbine.

Figure 1. Illustration of the location of the anchors, fairleads, and mooring lines. The position of the turbine p is indicated at the center of the platform.

2.2.1.3

The mooring force that acts on the floater is modeled with use of the OC4 design for a semisubmersible platform by NREL [26]. This design has three mooring lines oriented at 120° angles with respect to each other, and is schematically visualized in Figure 1. The mooring line anchors lie 200 meters below sea level, and by default, at a radial distance of 837.6 meters from the platform centerline in the horizontal plane. To adapt the stiffness of the mooring system this radial distance will be varied in the optimization. Shortening this radial distance while keeping the mooring line length constant results in slacker mooring lines, and hence a reduced stiffness of the mooring configuration. The total mooring force that acts on the platform equals the combined forces of the separate mooring lines:

$$F_{\text{mooring}}(p) = \sum_{i=1}^3 F_{\text{mooring},i}(p_{\text{anchor},i} - p_{\text{fairlead},i}(p)), \quad (2.5)$$

where the mooring force for each mooring line depends on the horizontal distance between the anchor and the fairlead of that mooring line. The force is evaluated based on interpolation from a lookup table provided along with the definition of the semi-submersible platform [26].

2.2.2 Wake modeling

FLORIDyn [1] is a dynamic parametric engineering model used to simulate the wake interaction between turbines at a low computational cost. To this end the model

Figure 2. Wind farm layout and mooring configuration. The anchoring radius which is varied in the optimization is indicated, and is equal to the distance from the platform center line to the anchor. Note that this a schematic representation, and that the proportions in this image are intentionally distorted.

employs so-called Observation Points (OP), which are created at each time step at each rotor center. Since the turbines move in this work, also the OP creation location changes, respectively. The OPs inherit the turbine state (e.g., yaw angle and turbine induction) at the time of their creation and travel with the free wind speed and direction downstream. Turbines located in the wake of other turbines use the passing OPs and their states to estimate the wind speed deficit resulting from the wake. The employed version of FLORIDyn¹ [2] uses the Gauss-Curl-Hybrid model to model the wind speed reduction. Note that no wake modifications have been made to the model to account for a possibly different wake recovery due to the turbine movement. This is justifiable for this preliminary study as the turbine speeds observed with the results are fairly slow. However, future work should further investigate this assumption.

2.2.3 Wind farm model

To complete the simulation environment, FLORIDyn is coupled to the floater model. To couple the models, FLORIDyn receives the location of the tower bases at every simulation time step from the floater model. Based on the position of the bases, FLORIDyn computes the effective wind speeds at these locations, and creates a new OP for each turbine originating from the location of its base. In turn, the floater model receives the effective wind speed from FLORIDyn and uses this to compute the aerodynamic force on the rotor for this time step. To compute the power at a given time step, the effective wind speed from FLORIDyn, and the velocity of the floater are used to compute the effective wind speed experienced by the turbine.

¹Code available at <https://github.com/TUDELFT-DataDrivenControl/OFF>

For all simulations performed in this work, an FWF consisting of two 5 MW turbines mounted on semi-submersible platforms is used. The turbines are spaced five rotor diameters apart, and the layout is schematically illustrated in Figure 2. The wind conditions are constant in time, and are equal in all simulations. The wind is assumed to be constant at 8.2 meters per second, and the wind direction is aligned with the positive x -axis. The distance r_{anchor} , indicated in Figure 2 serves as a measure to adapt the stiffness of the mooring system. In the original design, this distance is equal to 837.6 meters, and this distance can be decreased to slacken the mooring lines. Thereby the stiffness of the system can be changed. For all simulations in this work the turbines are initialized from an equilibrium position. Meaning that, prior to the simulation being started, the turbine positions are calculated for which the aerodynamic force on the rotor is in equilibrium with the mooring forces.

2.3 Description of the optimization problem

We will formulate an optimization problem with the goal to find the yaw signals that maximize the energy production of the wind farm over a period of 1800 seconds. To achieve this, the yaw signals are discretely sampled at a 25 second interval, and are provided to the optimizer as decision variables. For the two turbine wind farm the decision variables are therefore

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{1,0} & \gamma_{1,25} & \dots & \gamma_{1,1800} \\ \gamma_{2,0} & \gamma_{2,25} & \dots & \gamma_{2,1800} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 73}, \quad (2.6)$$

resulting in 73 decision variables per turbine. During the simulation, the yaw angles are linearly interpolated between the setpoints. Next, the cost function is defined as

$$J(\Gamma, r_{\text{anchor}}) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^T P_{i,j}, \quad (2.7)$$

where $P_{i,j}$ is the power produced by the i 'th turbine at the j 'th simulation time step. The cost is normalized by the total number of time steps T , and is therefore equal to the average power production of the wind farm. It is also indicated that the cost function depends on r_{anchor} , which determines the mooring configuration. The optimal yaw signals are defined with the following maximization criterion

$$\Gamma_{r_{\text{anchor}}}^* = \arg \max_{\Gamma} J, \quad (2.8)$$

where it is indicated that a set of yaw signals is only optimal with respect to a certain mooring configuration. To assess the effect of the anchoring radius on the optimal solution, the maximization criterion will be evaluated for different anchoring radii. Lastly, to formulate the full optimization problem, a yaw rate constraint is added

to guarantee continuity of the yaw signals, and a constraint on the maximum yaw excursion is added to guarantee validity of the vortex cylinder model of a yawed actuator disc. This results in:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\Gamma} J \\ \text{s.t.} & \begin{cases} \gamma_{i,0} = 0 & \forall i & \text{Initial condition} \\ |\gamma_{i,j}| \leq \phi & \forall i, j & \text{Constraint on the maximum yaw angle} \\ |\gamma_{i,j+1} - \gamma_{i,j}| \leq \theta & \forall i, j & \text{Constraint on the yaw rate} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

where the maximum yaw angle is fixed to ϕ , and the maximum yaw rate is fixed to 0.3 degrees per second. For the maximum yaw angle, two cases are studied. One case where $\phi = 45$ degrees, and a more restrictive case with $\phi = 20$ degrees. Also, a constraint is added to ensure that all simulations start from the same initial condition. To compare the results from this optimization problem to steady-state repositioning, we formulate a second optimization problem to find the optimal steady-state solutions:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\Gamma} J \\ \text{s.t.} & \begin{cases} |\gamma_{i,j}| \leq \phi & \forall i, j & \text{Constraint on the maximum yaw angle} \\ |\gamma_{i,j+1} - \gamma_{i,j}| = 0 & \forall i, j & \text{Constant yaw signals in time} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where to obtain the steady-state optimum, we assert that the yaw signals are constant in time. Also, the initial condition constraint is lifted.

2.4 Results

The optimization problem is solved for different locations of the mooring line anchors. To analyze the effect of mooring stiffness on the optimal repositioning solution, the optimization problem is solved for anchor radii in the range of 705 to 837.6 meters. Here, the stiffest configuration conforms to the OC4 mooring design. Also, to study the effect of limiting the maximum yaw angle, the optimization problem is solved for $\phi = 45$ and 20 degrees. The results of the optimization are presented in Figure 3. Here, the optimized wind farm power output is compared to the no control case, and compared to the power production with the optimal constant angles. In the figure, there are three regions indicated that refer to three optimal repositioning techniques, which will be discussed later.

It is most interesting to compare the constant yaw optima to the optimal solutions where time-varying yaw signals are allowed. For the slackest configurations, and for the tautest configurations, the optima with full yawing freedom are close to the constant yaw optima. However, for anchoring radii in the range of 750 to 810 meters,

Figure 3. The optimized wind farm power outputs compared to the no control case. The optimization result where the optimizer has all degrees of freedom is shown in dark blue for $\phi = 45$ degrees, and in light blue for $\phi = 20$ degrees. The optimization result where constant yaw angles are enforced is shown in orange. It is visible that for anchoring radii in the range of 745 to 815 meters the optimal solutions with full freedom significantly outperform the steady-state optima. Thus, for these cases it shows that it is suboptimal to apply steady-state techniques. Three regions are indicated, in each of which a different wake steering technique is optimal.

the optimal results where time-varying yawing is allowed drastically outperform the constant yaw optima.

We will show that there are in fact three wake steering techniques at play. In the first case, for the slackest configurations, it is optimal to perform steady-state turbine repositioning. Second, for the intermediate cases, it is optimal to dynamically yaw the turbines to achieve dynamic turbine repositioning. Third, for the most taut cases, it is again optimal to apply steady-state yaw signals. However, not with the goal of repositioning the turbines, but to perform conventional yaw steering which has been proposed for fixed-bottom wind farms. Each of the techniques is now treated in greater detail by looking at the optimal yaw control signals, and the optimal turbine trajectories.

2.4.1 Steady-state repositioning

The cases where steady-state turbine repositioning is optimal are shown in Figure 4. In this figure, the optimized yaw signals for $\phi = 45$ degrees, together with the crosswind turbine trajectories for an anchoring radius of 705 up to 745 meters are shown. From the figure, notice that the signals are close to a steady-state value for the majority of the optimization horizon. For steady-state turbine repositioning, the main wake steering mechanism is repositioning the turbines. Notice that the control of both turbines is equally important. This is because wake deflection caused by

yaw misalignment is counterproductive to the repositioning effect. Therefore, to achieve a crosswind distance between the turbines that is sufficient for the method to be effective, both turbines need to be repositioned. As the anchoring radius increases, the stiffness of the mooring system also increases. Therefore, from Figure 4 it is visible that more yawing effort is required to achieve a similar crosswind repositioning as the anchoring radius increases.

Figure 4. Optimal crosswind trajectories and optimal yaw signals for the mooring configurations with anchoring radius 705 to 745 meters, and $\phi = 45$ degrees. The optimal trajectories show a steady-state repositioning technique, where the upwind turbine is repositioned in the negative crosswind direction, and the downwind turbine is repositioned in the positive crosswind direction. Note that the optimal yaw signals are in steady-state apart from the beginning and the end of the optimization horizon.

2.4.2 Dynamic repositioning

By including wake dynamics in the analysis of turbine repositioning for stiffer mooring configurations, this work presents a novel floating turbine repositioning technique: dynamic repositioning. To illustrate dynamic repositioning, Figure 5 presents the optimal yaw signals and optimal crosswind trajectories for anchoring radii of 755, 785 and 805 meters, for the case $\phi = 45$ degrees. For the reason of conciseness, three of the six cases where dynamic repositioning is optimal are shown. For dynamic repositioning, notice that the optimal yaw solutions are periodic in nature, and lead to sinusoidal crosswind trajectories. By comparing the trajectories of the case with an anchoring radius of 755 meters in Figure 5a, to the cases with anchoring radius 785, and 805 meters, in Figures 5b and 5c respectively, it becomes visible that the optimal yawing frequency becomes larger as the mooring stiffness increases. Further analysis shows that the optimal yawing frequency is related to the natural frequency of the mooring system. In essence, the floater dynamics are those of a large nonlinear mass-spring-damper system. By linearizing the floater dynamics around their equilibrium positions with $\gamma = 0$, in Figure 6a, a Bode magnitude plot is made of the transfer function from the yaw angle to the crosswind position for each of the mooring configurations where dynamic repositioning is optimal. Notice that as the anchoring radius increases, the spring stiffness of the system increases, and thereby also the natural frequency of the system increases.

(a) Optimal solution for $r_{\text{anchor}} = 755$ meters

(b) Optimal solution for $r_{\text{anchor}} = 785$ meters

(c) Optimal solution for $r_{\text{anchor}} = 805$ meters

Figure 5. Optimal crosswind trajectories for anchoring radii 755, 785, and 805 meters and $\phi = 45$ degrees, showing a dynamic repositioning technique. Here the crosswind trajectories are sinusoidal, and the optimal yaw signals are periodic. Notice that for an increasing anchoring radius, and therefore an increasing mooring stiffness, the optimal yawing frequency increases.

It is important to mention that the nonlinear model has higher damping than the linearization, resulting in the gain at the natural frequency to be smaller for the nonlinear case.

Accompanying the figure is a table indicating how the natural frequencies relate to optimal yawing frequencies. To make this comparison, the natural frequency of the platform in crosswind direction, indicated by ω_0 , is compared to the frequency at which the yaw signal of the upwind turbine contains the most power, indicated by $\omega_{\gamma 1}$. This frequency is obtained by computing the power spectrum of the yaw signal, and taking the frequency that contains the most power. Notice that, while there is not a direct linear correlation, the optimal yawing frequency and the platform natural frequency are related.

Dynamic repositioning is capable of improving the wind farm efficiency by exploiting two features of the dynamics. Firstly, the optimal yaw signals are periodic close to the natural frequency of the mooring system. By yawing close to this frequency,

the magnitude of the crosswind trajectories is maximized. Secondly, the phase shift between the yaw signals alleviates the negative coupling between wake deflection from yaw misalignment, and wake deflection from repositioning. As the wake of the upwind turbine requires time to travel downstream, the effects of it are experienced by the second turbine with a time delay. The phase shift between the turbine trajectories is optimized such that the overlap of the upwind wake with downwind rotor is minimized over time.

Finally, notice from Figure 3, that for the case with a yaw limit of $\phi = 20$ degrees, the steady-state repositioning technique is optimal for the anchoring radius of 755 meters. Furthermore, for the anchoring radii of 765 and 775 meters, the gain in average power is less due to the yawing constraint. Hence, it can be seen that limiting the yaw action also limits the range where dynamic repositioning is effective.

Figure 6. Bode diagram of the linearized dynamics from the yaw angle in degrees, to the crosswind position in meters. The Bode diagram is plotted for the cases where dynamic repositioning is optimal, and the natural frequency of the linearized dynamics is indicated for each case. The table accompanying the plot displays the natural frequencies of the linearized dynamics, and compares them to the frequency that contains the most power in the power spectral density of the optimized yaw angles of the upwind turbine for the case where $\phi = 45$ degrees.

2.4.3 Yaw steering

For the most taut mooring configurations the optimizer prefers a technique that resembles conventional yaw steering. To illustrate this, Figure 7 presents the optimal yaw signals and crosswind trajectories for the anchoring radii of 815 and 835 meters. From this figure it is important to notice two things: first, the crosswind repositioning of both turbines is minimal, and second, the emphasis for the yaw control has shifted towards the upstream turbine. In Figure 7a, presenting the case with anchoring radius equal to 815 meters, the optimal yaw signals still contain some periodic yawing, and this case shows the transition of dynamic repositioning to conventional yaw steering. However, as Figure 3 indicates, this offers minimal

(a) Optimal solution for $r_{\text{anchor}} = 815$ meters

(b) Optimal solution for $r_{\text{anchor}} = 838$ meters

Figure 7. Optimal crosswind trajectories for anchoring radii 815 and 838 meters and $\phi = 45$ degrees, showing a conventional yaw steering technique. While the 815 meter case shows the transition from dynamic repositioning, in the 838 meter case the emphasis has almost completely shifted to yawing of the upwind turbine. Notice that the crosswind repositioning is minimal for these cases.

wind farm efficiency gain over steady-state yawing. By looking at the results for the 837.6 meter case in Figure 7b, the optimal yaw signals are approximately constant. Therefore, for the most taut cases, the optimal wake steering technique is conventional yaw steering, as the wind farm now more resembles a bottom-fixed farm.

2.5 Conclusion

Analysis with steady-state wake models has shown that mooring line tension needs to be reduced significantly for steady-state turbine repositioning to be effective. By performing an analysis with a dynamic wake model, this work concludes that, for the NREL 5MW turbine with a semi-submersible platform, also for stiffer mooring configurations a gain in wind farm efficiency can be made. For these stiffer mooring configurations it is shown that it is optimal to provide dynamic yaw signals to the turbines, that thereby result in dynamic turbine repositioning. By exploring the optimal yaw signals for various mooring configurations this work concludes that; for slack mooring configurations it is optimal to provide steady-state yaw signals to the turbines, for more taut mooring configurations it is optimal to provide dynamic yaw signals to the turbines, and for the tautest configurations it is optimal to perform traditional yaw steering.

For the dynamic repositioning technique to be feasible, mooring line tension still needs to be reduced comparative to the original OC4 semi-submersible design from

NREL. In the original design, the mooring line anchoring radius was set at 837.6 meters. Dynamic repositioning becomes feasible for anchoring radii smaller than 815 meters, and static repositioning becomes optimal for anchoring radii smaller than 755 meters. Because the slackest configurations, where the steady-state repositioning technique is optimal, provide higher wind farm efficiencies than the dynamic repositioning cases, dynamic repositioning provides a midway solution between decreasing mooring stiffness and increasing wind farm efficiency. For dynamic repositioning to be optimal, large yaw angles are required for some mooring configurations. With a more strict constraint on the maximum yaw angle, the range of mooring configurations where the technique is effective is slightly reduced.

This work has provided the first insights into dynamic repositioning. The objective for future research on this topic should be to validate the results from this work. Since a low-fidelity turbine model is used, it should be investigated if dynamic repositioning is feasible by performing simulations with higher fidelity models. Here, the influence of non-constant wind fields and of waves is also a topic of interest. Lastly, the focus of the optimization in this work has been on maximizing power production. For future work it is interesting to include other factors into the optimization. For example, the effects that these techniques have on mooring line fatigue and the interconnection with the grid.

3 PHASE SYNCHRONIZATION OF DYNAMIC TURBINE REPOSITIONING USING EXTREMUM SEEKING CONTROL

3.1 Introduction

Offshore wind energy has become an established energy source. In the period between 2010 and 2024, the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of offshore wind energy declined by 62%, and the global cumulative installed capacity increased from 3.1 GW to 82.9 GW [16]. To continue this growth, it is relevant that the majority of offshore wind energy resources are located in areas with water depths that exceed 60 meters [9], where the installation of fixed bottom turbines is economically unattractive. To access these resources, floating wind energy is expected to grow in the coming decades [11].

The efficiency of a wind farm is affected by wake interactions within the farm. That is because, as turbines extract energy from the wind, downwind turbines experience a lower wind speed and consequently produce less power. To optimize wind farm efficiency, wind farm flow control (WFFC) techniques have been developed that minimize wake interactions within the farm [23]. Unique to floating wind turbines is that a new mechanism for WFFC is possible: turbine repositioning [25, 22]. Floating wind turbines (FWTs) are not rigidly connected to the seabed, but are held in place by mooring lines, which allows the turbines a range of movement. Turbine repositioning leverages this range of movement to reposition turbines such that wake interaction is minimized. The conventional technique controls turbines to a steady-state optimum by repositioning the upstream and downstream turbine in opposite directions. Several studies demonstrated the potential of this technique [13, 14, 18], referred to as static repositioning. However, it is stressed that mooring lines need to be lengthened substantially beyond industry standards to facilitate a range of movement large enough for the technique to be effective. Recent work has shown that for tauter mooring configurations the optimal turbine repositioning strategy is dynamic [30]. Dynamic turbine repositioning periodically yaws both the upstream and the downstream turbine, causing a periodic variation in the thrust forces, which in turn yields periodic crosswind repositioning trajectories and meandering wakes.

For other WFFC techniques than turbine repositioning, dynamic control strategies are already established. Examples are the Pulse [12], the Helix [10] and dynamic yawing [24], which periodically change the magnitude or direction of the thrust force to enhance wake recovery. Similar to dynamic turbine repositioning, the control signals are periodic, and are typically defined by the actuation frequency ω , amplitude A , and in the case of an array of turbines, also the phase offset ϕ between turbines.

The implementation of dynamic WFFC strategies poses control challenges, primarily because optimal selection of these parameters depends on turbine properties, the wind farm layout, and also external conditions, like the wind speed, direction and turbulence intensity. Any model-based control strategy to adapt these parameters rapidly becomes intractable, as it relies on the simulation of complex large-scale aerodynamics, and requires accurate estimation of the wind conditions across the farm.

This work investigates the use of data-driven methods to achieve optimal dynamic WFFC with extremum seeking control (ESC). Extremum seeking control is a data-driven control technique that uses a periodic dithering signal to control a system to the optimum of a quasi-steady-state performance metric. Successful implementations to static WFFC already exist [6, 17], but the application to dynamic techniques has yet to be explored. To achieve data-driven dynamic WFFC, optimal ω , ϕ and A need to be maintained with respect to slow variations in wind conditions. For the Helix and the Pulse, optimal phase synchronization has been identified as most critical [33]. Therefore, this work provides the first step to data-driven dynamic WFFC by controlling the phase offset ϕ for dynamic turbine repositioning with ESC. To make this contribution, this work considers a two-turbine FWF consisting of IEA 15MW turbines, and uses the mid-fidelity simulation environment formed by QBlade [7], which is a coupled hydro-aero-elastic simulator for wind turbines, and SailFFish [27], which is a state-of-the-art free vortex particle wake model.

The contribution of this work spans two topics. First, this work contributes by presenting a closed-loop data-driven controller, by adapting ESC for optimal phase synchronization for dynamic WFFC techniques. Second, this work advances the knowledge on dynamic turbine repositioning, by investigating dynamic turbine repositioning control for different yawing frequencies and amplitudes in a simulation environment capable of accurately modeling wake and turbine dynamics.

The remainder of this work is structured as follows. First, an overview of the simulation environment used in this work is given in Section 3.2.1, and the fundamentals of ESC are given by Section 3.2.2. With this information, Section 3.3 designs the implementation of ESC to optimally control the phase offset for dynamic repositioning. Finally, the results are presented in Section 3.4, and the conclusions are given in Section 3.5.

3.2 Preliminaries

This section first provides a description of the simulation environment used in this work in Section 3.2.1. Subsequently, preliminaries on extremum seeking are provided in Section 3.2.2.

Figure 8. Schematization of the floating wind farm considered in this work. The wind farm is comprised of two IEA 15MW turbines mounted on VolturNUS platforms spaced 5 diameters apart. The volume simulated by SailFFish is indicated by the white box.

3.2.1 Simulation environment

For the analysis of turbine repositioning, this work considers a two-turbine FWF consisting of IEA 15MW turbines that are mounted on the semi-submersible VolturNUS platform, see Fig. 8. The turbines are spaced 5 diameters apart, and for all simulations, a constant laminar inflow of 8 m s^{-1} aligned with the positive x axis is used. The anchoring points of the mooring lines are oriented at angles 60° , 180° and 300° from the neutral position of the turbine, where the angle is defined clockwise from positive x axis. Further specifications regarding the mooring configuration used are given and motivated in Section 3.3.1. For the use of the wake model, a control volume is defined which spans $\{x_{\min}, x_{\max}\} \times \{y_{\min}, y_{\max}\} \times \{z_{\min}, z_{\max}\} = \{-2D, 15D\} \times \{-1.2D, 1.2D\} \times \{-1.2D, 1.2D\}$, with $D = 240$ (m) the rotor diameter, and defined from the neutral position of the upstream turbine at hub-height. The volume is divided into a Cartesian grid with $\{\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z\} = .05D$.

3.2.2 Extremum seeking control

This section provides an intuitive introduction to ESC, based on the work published in [31] and [29]. For an indepth coverage of ESC, the reader is referred to these works.

Extremum seeking control is a model-free control algorithm that optimizes the quasi steady-state input-output characteristics of a system, given a user defined performance criterion constructed from measured states of the system. The algorithm uses a periodic dither signal on the system input to perform a local exploration of the performance criterion. As a consequence of the dithering, the performance criterion is correlated with the dither signal, and using filtering and demodulation operations, this information is used to perform a gradient-based optimization of the criterion. For the application of ESC to dynamical systems, the algorithm relies on a separation of time scales, which are divided as

Figure 9. Block diagram illustrating a dynamical system subject to ESC control. The system has input u , disturbance v , and measurable states x . The performance criterion J maps the states into the performance metric y subject to optimization by ESC. The ESC implementation consists of an integrator, the filters $\mathcal{L}(s)$ and $\mathcal{H}(s)$, and dithering signals d_1 and d_2 .

- **Fast timescale:** Involving the system dynamics, and is typically defined by the slowest time constant of the system.
- **Medium-fast timescale:** Involving the periodicity of the dither signal
- **Slow timescale:** Involving slowly varying external disturbances acting on the system. In the context of WFFC, for example slow drifts in wind speed and direction.

With this separation of time scales, the system dynamics are regarded as quasi-steady state in the medium fast time-scale. The bandwidth of the extremum seeking controller is typically designed to also fall in this time-scale, and as an effect of this, the optimal input of the system is maintained with respect to the slower varying disturbances.

All elements required for the implementation of ESC are now explained with use of Fig. 9, which illustrates a dynamical system subject to ESC, with input u , measurable states x , and slowly varying disturbance v . The working mechanism of ESC is illustrated by briefly commenting on all elements of the figure in a clockwise manner. Starting from \tilde{u} , which is the desired steady-state input subject to control by ESC. The dither signal $d_1(t)$, which is this work is selected as a sinusoid with frequency ω and amplitude α , is added to obtain the input to the system. Next, the measurable states are used to evaluate the performance criterion $J(x)$, yielding the objective output y , which is subject to maximization. The periodic contribution of the dither signal is present in y , and ESC uses this information to estimate the gradient $\partial J / \partial \tilde{u}$. To achieve this, first y is detrended by the high-pass filter $\mathcal{H}(s)$,

after which it is multiplied by the demodulation signal $d_2(t, \psi)$. This demodulation signal has the same frequency as $d_1(t)$, but optionally lags in phase with an angle ψ , which is set by the user to compensate for any phase losses of the system, and the high-pass filter. The crucial insight that facilitates ESC, is that

- If $\partial y / \partial \tilde{u} > 0$, then $d_2(t)$ is positively correlated with \tilde{y} .
- If $\partial y / \partial \tilde{u} = 0$, then $d_2(t)$ is uncorrelated with \tilde{y} .
- If $\partial y / \partial \tilde{u} < 0$, then $d_2(t)$ is inversely correlated with \tilde{y} .

Therefore, by low-pass filtering the signal obtained after demodulation with $\mathcal{L}(s)$, the signal $\dot{\hat{u}}$ is an estimate of the desired gradient. By integrating $\dot{\hat{u}}$ over time, and multiplying with the integration gain κ , a gradient-based optimization scheme is achieved, and the feedback loop is completed.

To implement ESC, careful design of all elements is required. Specifically, the frequency and amplitude of the dither signal, the pass-bands of the filters $\mathcal{H}(s)$ and $\mathcal{L}(s)$, and the integration gain κ need to be designed. The implementation of ESC for dynamic repositioning is specified in Section 3.3.2.

3.3 Methods

To obtain a suitable mooring line design for dynamic repositioning, section 3.3.1 first analyzes the platform sway dynamic of the IEA 15MW turbine on the Voltur-nUS semi-submersible platform for different mooring configurations. Based on this analysis, a configuration is selected to be used for the remainder of simulations performed. Next, the design of ESC algorithm for the phase calibration of dynamic repositioning is motivated in Section 3.3.2.

3.3.1 Platform sway dynamics of IEA 15MW turbine

To analyze the platform sway dynamics, the crosswind repositioning response to a dynamic yaw signal is simulated for different frequencies and mooring line lengths. Consider Fig. 10, which presents the repositioning amplitude attained by sinusoidally yawing with an amplitude of 10° , with a wind speed of 8 m s^{-1} in the frequency range $1/1500$ to $1/90\text{Hz}$. Simulations are conducted for mooring line lengths of 850, which is the original design, up to 925 meters, in increments of 25 meters. Notice that the platform sway natural frequency increases for tauter mooring configurations, and that also the dynamics become less damped for tauter mooring, as is indicated by the more pronounced resonance peaks.

The remainder of this work considers the configuration with $l = 900$ meters. In this configuration, repositioning in the order of magnitude $D/10$ is possible, with D the rotor diameter. Increased lengthening of the mooring lines only yields additional repositioning for frequencies slower than $1/500 \text{ Hz}$, which are considered as

Figure 10. Frequency response to a sinusoidal yaw single with 10° amplitude of the platform sway dynamics for different mooring configurations. The mooring lines are incrementally lengthened with 25 meters compared to the original design.

very slow. The selected configuration provides significant additional displacement compared to the original design, but is considerably more taut than configurations typically used for static repositioning, where mooring lines are lengthened by more than 100 meters, e.g. [22, 25, 13, 14, 18].

3.3.2 Extremum seeking control for dynamic repositioning

This section provides the implementation of ESC to calibrate the phase difference in actuation between the upstream and downstream turbine for dynamic repositioning. A block diagram of the control scheme is illustrated in Fig. 11. To achieve dynamic repositioning, both turbines receive a sinusoidal yaw command with fixed frequency ω and amplitude A . To compare the performance of dynamic repositioning for several repositioning frequencies later in this work, and for applicability of the technique to other phase synchronization problems in WFFC, the ESC implementation is designed in terms of the repositioning frequency. The periodic nature of the yaw control signals, and the dither signal applied to ϕ has implications. This section first considers implications regarding the performance criterion, after which the effect of phase dithering is analyzed.

Before selecting appropriate parameters to implement the algorithm, a brief analysis of the performance objective is required. The objective of the controller is to maximize the energy production of the farm, which amounts to maximizing the *time averaged* power. However, because the applied yaw control signals are periodic with ω , also the power output of the farm fluctuates with this frequency, and harmonics of this frequency. The following conceptualization shows that without making any adaptations, ESC maximizes the time averaged power under mild conditions on the dithering frequency ω_d . For any fixed ϕ , and in the absence of noise,

Figure 11. Extremum seeking control implementation to control the phase difference for dynamic repositioning control

the power produced by the downstream turbine is a periodic signal with periodicity $T = 2\pi/\omega$, and hence can be expressed by its Fourier series

$$P_2(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \alpha_k(\phi) e^{jk\omega t}, \quad (3.1)$$

with $\alpha_k(\phi)$ the Fourier coefficients. Using the separation of time-scales, it is assumed that the coefficients $\alpha_k(\phi)$ are slowly varying as a consequence of the dithering, which holds for ω_d sufficiently smaller than ω . Without formal analysis, it is clear that all elements $\alpha_k(\phi) e^{jk\omega t}$, with $k \neq 0$, are orthogonal to the demodulation signal. Thereby only the variation in $\alpha_0(\phi)$ contributes to the extremum seeking scheme. As a result, ESC acts on the static component of P_2 , which exactly corresponds to the time-averaged power that is desired to be maximized.

The parameters for the ESC algorithm are designed by analyzing the effect of dithering on the phase ϕ . Using Fig. 11, the yaw angle for the downstream turbine is expressed as

$$\gamma_2(t) = A \cos(\omega t + \phi), \quad (3.2)$$

where the phase offset

$$\phi(t) = \tilde{\phi}(t) + \alpha \sin(\omega_d t), \quad (3.3)$$

consists of the steady-state component subject to control $\tilde{\phi}$, and the dither signal, defined by the dither amplitude α , and dither frequency ω_d . Notice that because ϕ is time-varying, the frequency of γ_2 is affected by the dither signal. To illustrate this, the argument of the cosine in (3.2) is differentiated with respect to time to define a *relative frequency* of γ_2

$$\hat{\omega}_2(t) = \omega + \alpha \omega_d \cos(\omega_d t) + \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}(t)}{\partial t}, \quad (3.4)$$

and it becomes clear that the range of $\hat{\omega}_2$ depends on the dithering amplitude and frequency, and that increasing α or ω_d increasingly influences the repositioning dynamics. To explore this consideration the bound $|\omega - \bar{\omega}| \leq \eta\omega$ is defined, where η determines the allowable frequency deviation from ω . Using (3.4),

$$\left| \alpha\omega_d \cos(\omega_d t) + \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}(t)}{\partial t} \right| \leq \eta\omega, \quad (3.5)$$

and by neglecting the influence of $\partial \tilde{\phi}/\partial t$, which is assumed to be slowly varying, $\omega_d \leq \eta\omega/\alpha$ is obtained. In view of this, and supported by empirical findings $\alpha = \pi/12$, and $\omega_d = \omega/4$ are selected, satisfying a bound of $\eta = \pi/48 \approx 6.5\%$. This dithering frequency satisfies the separation of timescales, and provides a balance between convergence speed, signal-to-noise ratio, and interference with the repositioning dynamics.

To finalize the implementation, the filters are defined as

$$\mathcal{H}(s) = \frac{s^2}{(s + \omega_{\text{cut-off}})^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{L}(s) = 1 - \mathcal{H}(s), \quad (3.6)$$

where the cut-off frequency is selected as $\omega_{\text{cut-off}} = 0.6\omega_d$, and the integration gain is empirically selected as $\kappa = 10\omega/\pi$. The phase offset on demodulation signal ψ , is set equal to zero, as the phase loss through the system at the dither frequency is negligible.

3.4 Results

To illustrate the performance of dynamic repositioning and the extremum seeking controller proposed in this work, the results in this section are divided into three parts. First, the extremum seeking controller is implemented for different repositioning frequencies and repositioning amplitudes. Second, to assess the accuracy of the proposed controller, the optimal phase offset is determined by means of a line-search, and the obtained results are compared to the results obtained with ESC. Third, to compare the effectiveness of dynamic repositioning to that of static repositioning for this mooring configuration, a grid search is performed to obtain the steady-state yaw angles that maximize the wind farm power.

The extremum seeking controller is implemented to calibrate the optimal phase offset for the repositioning frequencies $\omega \in \{2\pi/750, 2\pi/500, 2\pi/333\}$ rad/s. These frequencies correspond to the platform sway natural frequency, a lower frequency, and a higher frequency. For each frequency, the repositioning amplitudes $A \in \{10^\circ, 20^\circ\}$ are considered. The results for $A = 10^\circ$ are presented in Fig. 12a, and the results for $A = 20^\circ$ are presented in Fig. 12b. Both figures clearly indicate that for each case the wind farm power is maximized, and the phase offset approximately

Figure 12. Results of controlling the phase offset for dynamic repositioning with ESC, with yawing amplitudes of 10° (a), and 20° (b), and repositioning frequencies $\{2\pi/333, 2\pi/500, 2\pi/750\}$. The top plots show the time-averaged wind farm power, and the bottom-plot indicates the controller output ϕ .

Figure 13. Line search to find the optimal phase difference for dynamic repositioning for varying frequencies. The top row of plots display the total wind farm power, and the bottom row of plots indicates the crosswind repositioning trajectory of the downstream turbine. The repositioning amplitude of the upstream turbine is marked by the grey line

converges to a steady-state value. For both yawing amplitudes considered, the frequency $2\pi/333$ attains the highest power-output. To assess the accuracy of the proposed controller, a line search is conducted for each frequency, for the case $A = 20^\circ$. To achieve this, the phase offset of the downstream turbine is slowly varied over time. The results of this experiment are plotted in Fig. 13, where the wind-farm power is plotted in the upper row of plots, and the crosswind repositioning trajectory is plotted in the bottom row. Comparing the optimal values for ϕ to the values found by ESC shows that the controller converges to close proximity of the optimal value. Several further observations from this figure should be highlighted. First, observe that the case with $\omega = 2\pi/333$, consistently outperforms the other cases, regardless of the phase offset ϕ , thereby underlining the importance of selecting an appropriate frequency. Second, notice that for this frequency, the repositioning on the upstream turbine is considerably less compared to the other cases. Adding to

Figure 14. Grid search for the optimal steady-state yaw angles for static repositioning.

this, note that for each of the frequencies considered, the optimal phase offset does not yield maximal repositioning on the downstream turbine. These observations support that the maximizing repositioning does not necessarily maximize power.

To compare the dynamic repositioning results to static repositioning, a grid search is performed to find the optimal steady-state yaw angles, with a constraint of 20° on the maximum yaw allowed. The result of this is presented in Fig. 14. Notice that the optimal steady-state yaw angles are approximately $\gamma_1 = 20^\circ$, and $\gamma_2 = 10^\circ$, resulting in a power of 8.48 MW. When the yaw angle is limited to 10° , the maximum power obtained with static repositioning is 7.92. Comparing these results to dynamic repositioning shows that, both for a maximal yaw misalignment of 10° , and a maximal yaw misalignment of 20° , dynamic repositioning improves over static repositioning.

3.5 Conclusion

The conclusion of this work is threefold. First, this work demonstrated that ESC effectively maximizes the power, and achieves closed-loop phase synchronization for a two-turbine floating wind farm. Second, it is concluded that, for the mooring configuration considered, dynamic repositioning produces more power compared to static repositioning. Compared to 7.74 MW in the no-control case, dynamic repositioning produced 8.94 MW compared to 8.48 MW for static repositioning for a maximal yaw misalignment of 20° , and 8.21 MW compared to 7.92 MW for a maximal yaw misalignment of 10° . Third it is concluded that lower repositioning frequencies, for which larger crosswind displacement was obtained, result in a lower power gain compared to the higher-frequencies considered in this work, for which significantly less crosswind displacement was obtained. This suggests that the increased contribution of wake-mixing at higher frequencies outweighs the effects of increased repositioning at lower frequencies.

4 SYNCHRONIZED FLOATING HELIX CONTROL

In the previous two chapters of this deliverable, we demonstrated that synchronizing the motion of two wind turbines through dynamic wake steering constitutes a viable strategy for increasing the power output of a floating wind farm. In accordance with the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement, this chapter further investigates the potential of synchronized Helix control when applied at the floating wind farm level.

The results presented herein have not yet been published, in contrast to those discussed in the preceding chapters. Nevertheless, they represent a complementary and exploratory contribution that extends the methodological framework established earlier. In particular, this work illustrates how the approaches and analysis techniques developed in the previous chapters can be generalized and applied to synchronized Helix control, thereby broadening the scope of coordinated control strategies for floating wind farms.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. In Section 4.1 we briefly recap the Helix concept and the additional degree of freedom in a wind farm setting. In Section 4.2 we explain the simulation setup followed by the results in Section 4.3. We conclude this chapter with our conclusions.

4.1 The Helix and the role of the phase offset

In this section, the Helix is reintroduced [10]. The objective of the Helix is to enhance wake mixing. This is achieved by dynamically adjusting the individual blade pitch angles such that the wake behind the excited turbine is continuously manipulated.

The operating principle of the Helix is as follows. By independently adjusting the blade pitch angles, directional moments can be generated on the rotor. As a result, the aerodynamic moments can be controlled. For the Helix, this Tilt and Yaw moments are varied slowly in time, leading to a continuous change in wake direction. This approach is expected to promote wake mixing without inducing significant fluctuations in the magnitude of the rotor thrust force.

These moments are introduced by applying slowly varying sinusoids on the the Multi-Blade Coordinate (MBC) transformation [4]. This transformation decouples—or, equivalently, *projects*—the blade loads onto a non-rotating reference frame. Consequently, the measured out-of-plane blade root bending moments $M(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are expressed in a fixed reference frame. For a three-bladed turbine, the MBC transformation is defined as

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_0(t) & M_{\text{tilt}}(t) & M_{\text{yaw}}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}(\psi) \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} M_1(t) & M_2(t) & M_3(t) \end{bmatrix}}_{M(t)}, \quad (4.1)$$

with

$$\mathbf{T}(\psi) = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ \cos(\psi_1) & \cos(\psi_2) & \cos(\psi_3) \\ \sin(\psi_1) & \sin(\psi_2) & \sin(\psi_3) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Here, ψ_b denotes the azimuth angle of blade b , where $\psi = 0^\circ$ corresponds to the vertically upright blade position. The collective mode M_0 represents the total out-of-plane rotor moment, while M_{tilt} and M_{yaw} correspond to the fixed-frame, azimuth-independent tilt and yaw moments, respectively.

In an analogous manner, the inverse MBC transformation can be employed to obtain physically realizable blade pitch angles from fixed-frame collective, tilt, and yaw pitch inputs, denoted by θ_0 , θ_{tilt} , and θ_{yaw} , respectively:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \theta_1(t) & \theta_2(t) & \theta_3(t) \end{bmatrix}}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)} = \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\psi) \begin{bmatrix} \theta_0(t) & \theta_{\text{tilt}}(t) & \theta_{\text{yaw}}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.2)$$

with

$$\mathbf{T}^{-1}(\psi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos(\psi_1) & \sin(\psi_1) \\ 1 & \cos(\psi_2) & \sin(\psi_2) \\ 1 & \cos(\psi_3) & \sin(\psi_3) \end{bmatrix}.$$

The core idea of the Helix is to impose time-varying tilt and/or yaw moments on the rotor, thereby dynamically steering the turbine wake in the vertical and/or horizontal directions. To create the Helix, sinusoidal excitations are superimposed on θ_{tilt} and θ_{yaw} . The excitation frequency is typically chosen in the proximity of a Strouhal number of $St = 0.25$. This excitation is low-frequency, typically an order of magnitude lower than the rotor rotational frequency f_r .

If the tilt and yaw pitch inputs supplied to the inverse MBC transformation are constant in time, the resulting blade pitch angles $\theta(t)$ vary sinusoidally at the rotational frequency f_r . However, when θ_{tilt} and θ_{yaw} themselves vary sinusoidally with frequency f_e the resulting blade pitch signals exhibit a slightly modified frequency. From (4.2), the blade pitch angle $\theta_b(t)$ can be expressed as

$$\theta_b(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos(\psi_b) & \sin(\psi_b) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_0(t) \\ \theta_{\text{tilt}}(t) \\ \theta_{\text{yaw}}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

Within the FLOATECH project, the effects of the Helix control strategy have been studied extensively, with particular emphasis on the interaction between platform motion and the applied excitation frequency. These investigations focused on how the floater response influences the effectiveness of the Helix control. In the initial case studies, a fictitious downstream turbine was introduced to assess the potential power gains resulting from wake manipulation.

With the enhanced capabilities of the QBlade code (see Deliverable 3.1 [28]), it is now possible to explicitly model a second and even a third turbine operating within the wake of upstream turbines. This enables a more realistic assessment of wake interactions and allows the Helix control strategy to be applied not only to the first turbine but also to downstream turbines. Consequently, the impact of Helix control on the positioning of the wake and the associated power gains of the third turbine, as well as the overall wind farm performance, can be investigated.

In this extended configuration, an additional degree of freedom is introduced in the Helix control formulation, namely the phase of the Helix excitation applied to the second turbine relative to that of the first turbine. This phase offset governs the relative temporal alignment of the wake steering actions and is mathematically equivalent to:

$$\theta_0^1(t) = 0 \qquad \theta_0^2(t) = 0 \quad (4.4)$$

$$\theta_{\text{tilt}}^1(t) = A^1 \sin(2\pi f_e t) \qquad \theta_{\text{tilt}}^2(t) = A^2 \sin(2\pi f_e t + \textit{offset}) \quad (4.5)$$

$$\theta_{\text{yaw}}^1(t) = A^1 \cos(2\pi f_e t) \qquad \theta_{\text{yaw}}^2(t) = A^2 \cos(2\pi f_e t + \textit{offset}) \quad (4.6)$$

where the superscript refers to the turbine number and *offset* the offset of the Helix on the second turbine.

4.2 Simulation setup

This work investigates the synchronized application of Helix control in a three-turbine wind farm composed of IEA 15 MW reference wind turbines with flexible mooring lines. Each turbine features a rotor diameter of 240 m, and the turbines are aligned in the streamwise direction with an inter-turbine spacing of five rotor diameters. All simulations are performed under uniform inflow conditions with a constant free-stream wind speed of 8 m s^{-1} , allowing for a controlled assessment of

Figure 15. Simulation setup in Qblade

wake interaction effects. The analysis focuses on a baseline configuration in which the upstream turbine continuously applies Helix control, thereby actively manipulating its wake. This baseline is compared against scenarios in which the second turbine also deploys Helix control, while the upstream turbine operation remains unchanged. For the downstream turbine, the Helix excitation is applied with varying phase offsets relative to the upstream turbine. By systematically varying this phase offset, the study evaluates the influence of synchronized and phase-shifted Helix control on wake interaction, power production of the third turbine, and the overall wind farm performance.

4.3 Results

In this section we will present the results of the synchronized Helix approach. In Figure 16 we show the power of all the wind turbines compared with the baseline case as function of the phase offset on the second turbine.

In this figure you can see, as expected, that there is no difference between the baseline and the other cases for the first turbine since for the first turbine there is no difference. What it does show is that there are no numerical artifact influencing the outcome of the simulations. On the second turbine we deploy the Helix and here we see that the offset already has an effect on the power the second turbine produces. The general trend is that the power production decreases significantly (more than reported for bottom fixed wind turbines). However, if we look at the third turbine we see a significant increase with respect to the baseline for almost all phase offsets. If we now look at the additional power gain at this three wind turbine farm simulation we see a gain of 2.5% which is considered to be significant.

Figure 16. Power gain of the different turbines as a function of Helix offset on the second turbine

Figure 17. Variance of the tilt moment as a function of Helix offset on the second turbine

Figure 18. Variance of the yaw moment as a function of Helix offset on the second turbine

For the development of a control algorithm, it is also of interest to analyze the magnitude of the tilt and yaw moments acting on the individual turbines as a function of the phase offset. Figures 17 and 18 present the variance of the tilt and yaw moments, respectively. As these signals are predominantly sinusoidal, the variance serves as an appropriate proxy for their amplitude.

A consistent behavior is again observed for the first turbine, showing little sensitivity to the phase offset. In contrast, the second turbine exhibits a pronounced dependence on the phase offset, indicating that the periodic bending moments induced by the unsteady inflow from the upstream turbine can be either amplified or mitigated through appropriate phase selection. The third turbine also shows an increase in periodic loading, although the effect is less pronounced than for the second turbine.

When comparing the phase offsets that yield maximum power gains with those that minimize the variance of the bending moments, no clear correlation can be identified, making it difficult to draw a definitive conclusion.

4.4 Conclusion

The results presented in this work demonstrate that synchronized Helix flow control exhibits significant potential for improving wind farm performance. Compared to the baseline configuration in which only the upstream turbine deploys Helix control, the synchronized application of Helix control on multiple turbines yields additional energy gains of 2.5%. These findings highlight the importance of platform dynamics and their coupling with wake manipulation strategies in floating wind farms.

Future research should extend the present analysis by incorporating turbulent in-flow conditions to assess the robustness of synchronized Helix control under more realistic atmospheric scenarios. In addition, the use of dedicated synchronization algorithms—such as those presented in [34, 35]—should be investigated to dynamically coordinate the phase relationship between turbines. As an alternative approach, the extremum-seeking control (ESC) methods described in the previous section could be implemented to adaptively optimize the Helix control parameters in real time, thereby maximizing farm-level performance without requiring explicit wake or flow models.

5 CONCLUSION

This deliverable, which is based on two scientific publications, presents the work performed for Task 3.2 of the FLOATFARM project. The primary objective of this task is to research cooperative control for floating wind turbines. To this end, a two-step approach was taken, where first Chapter Chapter 2 investigated the use of simple nonlinear models, and linear analysis techniques, to find the optimal turbine repositioning control strategy of a two-turbine wind farm depending on mooring line stiffness. Second, in Chapters 3 and 4, synchronized control for turbine repositioning, and for the Helix, was tested and validated in the mid-fidelity simulation environment developed as part of Task 3.1 of the FLOATFARM project.

The first conclusion of this report is that analysis with engineering models shows that the optimal turbine repositioning control strategy critically depends on the tension of the mooring lines of the floating wind farm, as is discussed in Chapter 2 of this Task. Depending on the mooring configuration, three strategies are identified to maximize the power of the farm. Firstly, for taut mooring configurations, negligible turbine repositioning is possible, and it is shown that the optimal strategy is to perform conventional yaw steering, similar to a bottom-fixed wind farm. Secondly, for medium-taut mooring configurations, it is optimal to perform dynamic turbine repositioning, and provide periodic yaw signals to both the upstream and the downstream turbine. Thirdly, for slack mooring configurations it is optimal to perform static turbine repositioning. An important insight is that static turbine repositioning only becomes feasible when turbines can be repositioned across large distances. Therefore, for medium taut mooring configurations, where the range of repositioning is limited, dynamic turbine repositioning provides a solution to maximize power. For the dynamic turbine repositioning strategy, both the upstream and the downstream turbine receive periodic yaw angles, resulting in periodic repositioning of the turbines. Based on analysis with linear models, it was concluded that the optimal frequency to reposition the turbines is related to the sway natural frequency of the floater, and that the phase difference in the actuation is critical to the performance of the technique.

The second conclusion of this report is that the newly proposed dynamic turbine repositioning strategy is shown to be effective in a mid-fidelity simulation environment, and that the control of the turbines is effectively synchronized with extremum seeking control. In Chapter 3, the majority of the conclusions obtained with the low-fidelity simulation environment in Chapter 2 were validated. It was shown that for a two-turbine wind farm consisting of IEA 15MW turbines mounted on the Volturus platform, where the mooring lines are lengthened with 50 meters, dynamic turbine repositioning outperforms static repositioning, with 8.9 MW compared to

8.5 MW, respectively, compared to 7.75 MW in the no-control case. This supports the conclusion that for medium-taut mooring configurations, it is optimal to apply dynamic turbine repositioning. However, where in Chapter 2 it was hypothesized that the optimal repositioning frequency was related to the platform sway natural frequency, the mid-fidelity simulations did not support this. The highest frequency of the three frequencies considered, with a frequency 1.5 times faster than the natural frequency, showed the highest power gain. A detailed analysis of the physical mechanisms underlying the dynamic repositioning strategy is required to provide further insight, which will be performed as part of Task 3.3 of the FLOATFARM project.

The third conclusion of this work is that synchronizing the control of the Helix for multiple turbines significantly affects the efficiency of the farm. A three turbine floating wind farm is considered, where the first and second turbine are controlled with the Helix, and the phase of the Helix actuation on the second turbine is subject to optimization. Depending on the phase of Helix of the second turbine, it is shown that the Helix interacts constructively or destructively with the incoming wake, which has significant effects on the loads on the second turbine, and the power output of the third turbine.

In conclusion, this report showed that the optimal yawing strategy of a floating wind farm depends on the mooring configuration. The proposed strategies were validated in a mid-fidelity simulation environment, and it was shown that effective closed-loop cooperative control is achieved with extremum seeking control. Furthermore, it is concluded that the synchronization of the Helix for a floating wind farm has significant significant effect on the power output of the farm.

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